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The Study of Policy Implementation on Teaching Observation in Darasamutr School Sriracha, Chon Buri, Thailand

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the level of policy implementation on teaching observation in Darasamutr School, Thailand. It likewise explored the factors affecting such level of implementation. Three population samples were considered for the study, namely elementary teachers, high school teachers and administrators. Perceptions among these sample groups on the level of policy implementation were statistically compared. Data collected from a total of 234 respondents revealed a consistent observation on the high level of policy implementation on teaching observation on the said campus. Significant differences however were noted along ethical protocols specifically between elementary teachers and administrators. The top three factors identified to be potentially affecting the level of policy implementation were Teacher factor, Evaluation tool factor and Miscellaneous factor. Furthermore, some administrative challenges were identified by the administrator respondents. The study's conclusion points to some key areas along the implementation process needing review and revision. Relevant recommendations were then endorsed in order to facilitate optimal effectiveness and relevance of teacher evaluation. Finally, a concept map was drawn to highlight the proposed process flowchart for the campus implementation on teaching evaluation and observation.

Keywords: Teacher Evaluation, Classroom observation, Policy Implementation, Darasamutr School, Chon Buri, Thailand

1. Introduction

1.1. Global mandate for quality education

High quality education is essential for optimal learning and human development. Equitable and quality education in particular, is one of the United Nations' 17 Global Goals embedded in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (SDG4). This SDG4 lists Seven (7) outcome targets and Three (3) means of

implementation. Means #1 calls for effective learning environments while means # 3 calls for a substantial increase in the supply of qualified teachers especially in least developed countries by year 2030 (UNESCO).

Among developing nations however, poor quality education is one of the myriad socioeconomic problems. UNESCO's claim of a *global learning crisis* was brought about by poor quality education. In its 11th Education for All Global Monitoring Report, it was estimated that 175 millions of young people in poor countries are suffering from illiteracy. In Asia, around 74 Million children have no primary education according to UNICEF. Furthermore, this *learning crisis* is said to be costing governments a hefty sum of \$129 Billion a year (Pauline Rose, 2014).

The gaps along evidence-based methods such as performance evaluations vis a vis quality education has been huge and polarizing. Take for example the premise that teachers quality has been positively linked to student learning (Robinson,2018)⁴ but questions such as "What makes a good teacher?" or "What makes a good education system?" put the value of performance evaluations in a grey zone. The concept of "educational accountability" being put upon teachers expands the argument into personnel and systems management (e.g., who's responsible for the teachers?). Further debates loom as to the ideal parameters and settings for teacher's performance evaluations. Henceforth, teacher's evaluation reform becomes a much more relevant issue. This study thus aims to contribute to the pool of knowledge on the importance of teacher evaluations and education reform especially in one of Asia's rapidly developing country like Thailand.

As reported by Forwerck, of The Borgen Project (2017), Thailand has 97.6% literacy rate as enhanced by the national free education access under the 1999 Education Act. Global academic ratings show that Thai students scored *below* the global average on PISA tests in 2014, ranking 35th out of 40 countries. Likewise, reports from the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) also indicate that the country has fallen behind relative to its Asian neighbors. Yet, government spending on education was shown the highest among ASEAN countries at 22.3% of government expenditure (Michael, R. 2018) This figure even reflects an increase from 19.35% in the year 2015 (Sagarik, D. 2014). Statistica cited a hefty budget in 2015 with 559.43Billion Baht. The Bangkok Post (2020) reported the highest in 2018 with 816.46 billion baht or 5% of its GDP. This has catapulted Thailand as the world's top spender and yet one of the worst performers in education. Thailand's educational system is ranked 35th among 40 countries included in 2014 (Lao, R. 2017).

1.2. Framing teacher evaluation in education reform agenda

According to the former director-general of WTO, Supachai Panitchpakdi, Thailand's education system is a "total failure" despite the massive spending (Asia news it, 2016). One cause cited was the huge gap between Bangkok and the rural areas which fall short far below national standards. His tone had set the alarm for the nation's education emergency. The implication points to the urgency for local education reform agenda.

In another APEC report, the MOE showcased Thailand's education reform roadmap (Figure 1) identifying its short-term as well as long-term plans.

Educational reforms have been a trend in the improvement of the educational system. Policies are constantly being formulated to support these reforms. Thus, there is a need to evaluate the level of policy implementation since policy creation is not the end of a reform but just a start. The level of implementation would determine if the goal for reform is being met (Viennet & Pont, 2017).

Local studies on teacher observation in Thailand have been scant. Relevant researches were done by Narathakoon et al., (2020), Harrowell (2019) and Pillay (2002). The research gap on teacher evaluations is huge. As such this study is an attempt to contribute to the body of knowledge on the topic of teacher observation.

Figure 1: Thailand's Education Reform

Source: Roadmap (MOE 2014)

1.3. Statement of the Problem

Generally, this study aimed to develop a concept map for optimal Policy Implementation on Teaching Observation in Darasamutr School Sriracha, Chon Buri, Thailand.

Specifically, the study aims to satisfy the following problems;

1. What is the level of policy implementation on teaching observation in Darasamutr School Sriracha, Chon Buri as perceived by the following:
 - a) School administrators
 - b) Primary teachers
 - c) Secondary teachers
2. Is there a significant difference between the perceived level of policy implementation on teaching observation among School administrators; Primary Teachers and Secondary Teachers
3. What are the factors affecting the level of policy implementation on teaching observation in Darasamutr School Sriracha?
4. Is there a significant difference between the factors identified in affecting the level of policy implementation on teaching observation?
5. What administrative setup (concept map) can be proposed to enhance the level of the policy implementation on teaching observation in Darasamutr School Sriracha ?

1.4. Hypothesis of the study

This study assumes the following hypotheses.

1. There is no significant difference between the perceived level of policy implementation on teaching observation among school administrators, primary and secondary teachers.
2. There is no significant difference between the factors identified in affecting the level of policy implementation on teaching observation.

1.5. Scope and Limitation

Given the limitations of time and resources and the pandemic travel and transaction protocols, this study is expected to be limited in terms of the scope of respondents. It, therefore, aims to go about data gathering in a more limited number than projected but in a more intensive rather than extensive manner, without compromise to the quality of data. Furthermore, this study merely aims to determine the level of policy implementation and the factors affecting the level and manner of such implementation in one school.

1.6. Definition of Terms

Administrators: A person whose job is to manage a company, school, or other organizations (Mirriam-Webster Dictionary).

Performance Evaluation: Performance evaluation per se is defined as a formal and productive procedure to measure an employee's work and results based on their job responsibilities (Questionpro, 2021). To be more specific, teacher's evaluation is defined as the standardized process or rating and assessing the teaching effectiveness of educators (Safety culture, 2021).

Classroom Observation: Classroom observation on the other hand is defined as an assessment technique (CAT) used in gauging student interaction and how or what they are learning. It is geared towards satisfying a given set of indicators aligned towards performance targets (McMillan, 2015). In addition, this process is also known as *learning walks* or *walkthroughs* is typically conducted by administrators or instruction specialists as an extension of job performance evaluations. The duration may last from a few minutes to a full class period or rarely, a school day. Furthermore, educators may use a variety of classroom observation methods and templates from nationally utilized models to homegrown, institutional ones (glossary of education reform, 2013).

Education reform: Refers to any planned changes in the way a school or school system functions, from teaching methodologies to administrative processes (RAND, 2020).

Policy Implementation: Refers to the stage in the whole process of translating the goals and objectives of a policy into action. This also entails reference to a pre-approved set of terms of laws (community dictionary, 2021).

Policy: A definite course of action planned or adopted for the sake of expediency, facility and others. (dictionary.com).

Policy Makers: Someone who creates ideas and plans, especially those carried out by a business or government. A mayor, a school board, a corporation's board of directors, and the President are all policy makers (Vocabulary.com)

1.7. Conceptual framework

Policy implementation is a complex process. More so, when it is linked to bigger outcomes such as education reform. The concept of implementation per se connotes the existence of a standard to be followed and to be placed in action. These standards are ideals agreed upon by consensus of so called policy makers. Implementation analysis likewise implies some evaluation of the process and players involved.

Figure 2 presents this study's conceptual framework considering the OECD national framework.. The need for an efficient and effective teachers evaluation and performance assessment is just another phase in the whole process of educational transformation. Tracing up the ladder is the global mandate for quality education as stipulated by the UN-UNICEF SDG global goal # 4. Thailand as one of the less performing countries along this global goal has a lot of reform work to do. Reform on the level of school management as well as well as national education system. Modest upgrades in the systems of policy implementation along teachers performance is already a huge success when undertaken with sustained momentum. Ultimately, the goal is quality education for all and it can begin with a balanced view of improving teachers' performance along with the students' outcomes or performance both locally and internationally.

2. Methods and Materials

This study was designed as descriptive research that determined the level of policy implementation on teaching observation in Darasamutr School, Thailand. A total of 234 respondents composed of primary teachers (87), secondary teachers (108), and administrators (39) were surveyed and interviewed with consent/ The self-made questionnaire was translated in Thai and pretested with a reliability test result of .719 (Cronbach's Alpha). A 4-point Likert scale was used to measure the level of policy implementation. After data gathering, cleaning and coding, statistical tools used ranged from weighted means to ranking, F- test, Kruskal-Wallis and Marascullio. Other data collection paraphernalia included a voice recorder, a field notebook and a laptop. For purposes of face validity, two educators were asked to evaluate the questionnaires before it was administered to the students

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 The level of policy implementation on teaching observation

The level of policy implementation on teaching observation in Darasamutr School Sriracha, Chon Buri as perceived by the School administrators ,Primary teachers and Secondary teachers is generally, *Fully Implemented*. This was interpreted as per the tool rubrics as *Excellent or Perfectly executed*. This outcome sets a very good impression on the school's administration as well as policy implementation standards along with areas of Scope, Duration & Timeliness, Ethical Protocol, Feedback and Education Standards. It likewise revealed a consistent and comprehensive policy implementation on campus.

POLICY & PRACTICE	Elementary Teachers (n = 87)			Secondary Teachers (n = 108)			Administrators (n = 39)			Overall (N = 234)		
	M	SD	VI	M	SD	VI	M	SD	VI	M	SD	VI
A. SCOPE												
1. All teachers from every school level are regularly evaluated/observed.	4.56	0.68	F	4.65	0.62	F	4.79	0.52	F	4.64	0.63	F
2. All Thai teachers and Foreign teachers are observed with the same evaluation criteria or rubrics.	4.54	0.63	F	4.56	0.60	F	4.64	0.63	F	4.56	0.61	F
3. All Thai teachers and Foreign teachers are observed with the same evaluation committee.	4.48	0.78	F	4.49	0.74	F	4.72	0.51	F	4.53	0.72	F
4. All members (3) of the evaluation committee are present consistently/every time.	4.46	0.63	F	4.47	0.70	F	4.74	0.59	F	4.51	0.66	F
Sub-Area Mean	4.51	0.57	F	4.54	0.57	F	4.72	0.49	F	4.56	0.56	F
B. DURATION and TIMELINESS												
5. Classroom Observation is done once regularly per semester.	4.70	0.49	F	4.77	0.56	F	4.77	0.48	F	4.74	0.52	F
6. Classroom observation period is conducted as prescribed and the same for all teachers regardless of status, background, school level taught.	4.61	0.64	F	4.57	0.53	F	4.74	0.50	F	4.62	0.57	F
7. Classroom observation period is conducted at an optimal and convenient time for both students and teachers.	4.56	0.66	F	4.64	0.54	F	4.82	0.39	F	4.64	0.57	F
Sub-Area Mean	4.62	0.52	F	4.66	0.43	F	4.78	0.39	F	4.67	0.46	F
C. ETHICAL PROTOCOL												
8. The observation timeline is generally announced through memos or during meetings.	4.48	0.63	F	4.46	0.74	F	4.56	0.68	F	4.49	0.69	F
9. The teacher concerned is cordially informed of the date and time slot of observation.	4.62	0.58	F	4.59	0.66	F	4.67	0.66	F	4.62	0.63	F
10. The teachers were oriented and provided with a copy of the evaluation tool to be used.	4.26	0.75	F	4.48	0.73	F	4.62	0.59	F	4.42	0.73	F
11. The observation process is conducted in a highly professional and objective manner.	4.39	0.69	F	4.58	0.60	F	4.67	0.66	F	4.53	0.65	F
Sub-Area Mean	4.44	0.52	F	4.53	0.54	F	4.63	0.55	F	4.51	0.53	F
D. FEEDBACK												
12. A post conference is regularly conducted by administrators or evaluation committee.	4.20	0.74	H	4.30	0.81	F	4.41	0.59	F	4.28	0.76	F
13. Performance Evaluation results are objectively used for merit system (promotion /retention) as well as identifying personnel development areas.	4.24	0.78	F	4.32	0.78	F	4.49	0.79	F	4.32	0.78	F
14. Concerns or issues forwarded regarding observation or evaluation is openly discussed among teachers and fairly resolved by administrators concerned.	4.08	0.89	H	4.28	0.77	F	4.28	0.83	F	4.21	0.83	H

	Sub-Area Mean	4.1 7	0.6 9	H	4.3 0	0.69	F	4.3 9	0.6 1	F	4.2 7	0.68	F
E. EVALUATION STANDARD													
15.	The observation tool is aligned or at par with Thai national education standards	4.4 1	0.6 7	F	4.4 9	0.63	F	4.6 9	0.4 7	F	4.5 0	0.63	F
16.	The observation tool used is comprehensive, suitable and useful in assessing the teachers' classroom performance.	4.4 6	0.7 3	F	4.5 2	0.60	F	4.6 9	0.4 7	F	4.5 3	0.64	F
17.	The evaluation tool is revised for upgrading to keep abreast with any changes relevant to the performance criteria (e.g., new curriculum/policy).	4.4 5	0.7 4	F	4.4 3	0.66	F	4.6 2	0.4 9	F	4.4 7	0.67	F
	Sub-Area Mean	4.4 4	0.6 7	F	4.4 8	0.58	F	4.6 7	0.4 0	F	4.5 0	0.59	F
	Overall Mean	4.4 4	0.5 3	F	4.5 1	0.47	F	4.6 4	0.4 0	F	4.5 1	0.48	F

Legend: F: Fully Implemented; M: mean SD: Standard Deviation ; VI: Verbal Interpretation

3.2 Significant difference between the perceived level of policy implementation on teaching observation among School administrators, Primary Teachers, Secondary Teachers

There is no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the perception of how the policies and practices related to policy implementation are implemented in terms of the rank status of the respondents. The same is true along with scope, duration, timeliness, ethical protocol, feedback and evaluation standard among the respondents ($p > 0.05$). However, along with ethical protocol, there is a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between the elementary teachers and administrators in terms of their perception of how “the teachers were oriented and provided with a copy of the evaluation tool to be used” and “the observation process is conducted in a highly professional and objective manner.”

3.3 Factors and Challenges affecting the level of policy implementation on teacher observation

The Factors affecting the level of policy implementation on teaching observation in Darasamutr School Sriracha ranged from categories of internal to external and miscellaneous factors (table 1). Rankings revealed that the *Teacher factor* (1st) and the *Evaluation tool* (2nd) factor were the top most important factors identified by the respondents. Miscellaneous came in the middle (3rd) while student and administrative factors were ranked as the least important or dependent factors affecting the evaluation outcomes. Top Sub factor identified for the Teacher factor category was an item on *Teacher's awareness of the policies or matters regarding teaching observation/ evaluation*. Meanwhile for the Evaluation tool factor category, it was the item *on Appropriateness of the tool to the teacher concerned (e.g. correct evaluation form was used or if the teacher concerned needs to be evaluated)*. Under the Miscellaneous factor category, it was the *Physical set up or ambiance* that was ranked as most important. Meanwhile, the administrative Challenges identified affecting the level of policy implementation on teaching observation in Darasamutr School Sriracha ranged from themes of time management/constraints to lack of feedback and classroom management concerns especially from the elementary teachers. Elements pertaining to physical set up like Technical malfunctions during observations were also mentioned. Evaluation rubric transparency issues as well as concerns on the lack of evaluation tool validity were listed.

Table 1: Summary of Factors affecting Policy Implementation on Teaching Observation

Factor categories	Elementary Teachers (n = 87)		Secondary Teachers (n = 108)		Administrators (n = 39)		Overall (N = 234)		Rank
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
I. INTERNAL FACTORS									
A. TEACHER FACTOR									
a. Teacher's awareness on the policies or matters regarding teaching observation/evaluation.	83	95.40	108	100.00	39	100.00	230	98.29	1
b. Teacher's personal background like age, years of teaching experience, gender, etc.	68	78.16	82	75.93	32	82.05	182	77.78	
c. Teacher's employment status (e.g. full time/part-time/regular/contractual)	70	80.46	84	77.78	31	79.49	185	79.06	
d. Teacher's availability of visual aids and materials for classroom observation	83	95.40	106	98.15	38	97.44	227	97.01	3
e. Teacher's physical and mental health state during evaluation period	81	93.10	96	88.89	37	94.87	214	91.45	
f. Teacher's stress level and anxiety during classroom evaluations	62	71.26	91	84.26	30	76.92	183	78.21	
g. Teacher's attitude towards teaching performance evaluations/observations	79	90.80	100	92.59	36	92.31	215	91.88	
h. Teacher's mastery of the subject matter/course taught	84	96.55	106	98.15	38	97.44	228	97.44	2
i. Teacher's support system (e.g. family/friends /colleagues)	78	89.66	95	87.96	35	89.74	208	88.89	
B. STUDENT FACTOR									
a. Student's awareness of the teacher's classroom observation schedule (e.g. teacher informed them beforehand of visitor's arrival)	76	87.36	97	89.81	38	97.44	211	90.17	3
b. Student's level of exposure on classroom observations	82	94.25	96	88.89	37	94.87	215	91.88	2
c. Student's class profile (e.g. year level/grade/section)	81	93.10	90	83.33	32	82.05	203	86.75	
d. Student's level of comprehension or understanding as to the purpose of classroom observations	84	96.55	101	93.52	36	92.31	221	94.44	1
e. Student's personal attitude towards the teacher or the subject matter	83	95.40	93	86.11	34	87.18	210	89.74	
C. ADMINISTRATIVE FACTORS									
a. Administrator's level of moral support towards teachers with regards to teaching evaluations	80	91.95	96	88.89	37	94.87	213	91.03	2
b. Administrator's level of information dissemination as to the policies and guidelines relevant to classroom observation	78	89.66	95	87.96	39	100.00	212	90.60	3
c. Administrator's ability to conduct post conference with their respective subordinates	82	94.25	95	87.96	39	100.00	216	92.31	1
d. Administrator's ability to resolve any issues /complaints regarding	82	94.25	97	89.81	37	94.87	216	92.31	1

performance evaluations										
II. EXTERNAL /MISCELLANEOUS FACTORS										
A.	Physical set up / classrooms	84	96.55	102	94.44	38	97.44	224	95.73	1
B.	Time slots /timing of classroom observation	84	96.55	99	91.67	36	92.31	219	93.59	2
C.	Demeanor /Personality of the observer (evaluation committee)	82	94.25	95	87.96	31	79.49	208	88.89	
D.	Technological /visual aids malfunction	77	88.51	97	89.81	36	92.31	210	89.74	3
III. EVALUATION TOOL FACTOR										
A.	Transparency of rubrics used in the evaluation tool	85	97.70	103	95.37	38	97.44	226	96.58	2
B.	Comprehensiveness of the criteria used in the evaluation tool	80	91.95	101	93.52	39	100.00	220	94.02	3
C.	Appropriateness of the tool to the teacher concerned (e.g. correct evaluation form was used)	85	97.70	104	96.30	38	97.44	227	97.01	1

Figure 2 presents a thematic Venn diagram of the challenges based on the administrator interviews. These challenges ranged from time constraints to the sheer number of students per class.

The consequences of such challenges thus ranged from minor lapses or inefficiencies in the evaluation to transparency issues. Although some administrative solutions were suggested with regards to addressing these challenges and mitigating the unintended consequences, some issues still lack definite solutions. From an administrator's perspective however, it is apparent that evaluation standards are indirectly compromised by the level and efficiency of process implementation. Evaluation Policy implementation is indeed a complicated administrative endeavor. As one respondent stated, "*no perfect system exists.*"

Figure 2: Thematic diagram of the administrative challenges affecting the level of policy implementation on teacher observation

Despite facing these challenges, the administrators voiced encouragement for cooperation and work dedication from the teachers. Accepting willingness for internal reform has been signified by the responses but as one administrator comments “no perfect system” exists. James (2021) corroborates as to the difficulty of evaluations, saying that it is in fact “*an imperfect task.*”

3.4 Significant difference between the factors identified in affecting the level of policy implementation on teaching observation

There are statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between elementary teachers and administrators in terms of identifying the factors that affect the policy implementation on teaching observation. Such is on the “student’s awareness of the teacher’s classroom observation schedule (e.g. teacher informed them beforehand of visitor’s arrival)” along with student factors, “administrator’s level of information dissemination as to the policies and guidelines relevant to classroom observation” along with administrative factors, “demeanor /personality of the observer (evaluation committee)” along with external/miscellaneous factors and “comprehensiveness of the criteria used in the evaluation tool” along with evaluation tool factors. There are also statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between secondary teachers and administrators in terms of identifying the factors that affect the policy implementation on teaching observation. Such is on the “administrator’s level of information dissemination as to the policies and guidelines relevant to classroom observation” and “administrator’s ability to conduct post conference with their respective subordinates” under administrative factors and “comprehensiveness of the criteria used in the evaluation tool” under evaluation tool factors.

4. Conclusion

Based on the general findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The *fully implemented* level of policy implementation on teaching observation in Darasamutr School Sriracha, Chon Buri sets a very good impression on the school’s administration as well as policy implementation standards. It likewise revealed a consistent and comprehensive policy implementation in the campus.

As indicated by the statistically significant difference among elementary teachers and administrators, it can be further concluded that these teachers are quite sensitive and needful of orientation on the evaluation tool to be used. In addition, there is a need among the said respondents to be mindful of the professional and objective conduct of the evaluations. This further indicates the teachers’ sensitivity towards fairness and non-biased performance assessment.

The Factors affecting the level of policy implementation on teaching observation in Darasamutr School Sriracha gravitated more towards *teacher factor* and *Evaluation tool factor*. This reflects the general notion that evaluation outcomes are more dependent on the teacher and the evaluation tool. While miscellaneous and administrative factors are similarly recognized, their rankings indicated a less active role in the evaluation outcomes as perceived by the respondents.

The administrative challenges in the evaluation policies implementation point to the need for time management especially among the evaluation committee. The need for a feedback mechanism was likewise voiced out among teachers.

Finally, Elementary teachers tend to show some special needs given the nature of their students. The students need to be oriented as to the purpose and mechanics of classroom observation is apparent. Rubrics therefore might suggest an age-based approach.

5. Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are presented:

The level of policy implementation in Darasamutr School Sriracha, Chon Buri must be maintained to the highest level .As such, implementation policies and practices maybe ripe for benchmarking to other campuses or schools of similar or even different pedagogy. Information dissemination thru meetings ,memos and non-formal means , on evaluation policies and procedures must be ramped up at all school levels. Likewise, measures to ensure and assure the teachers of the professorial conduct of the evaluations must be on the top agenda. A timely review of the evaluation tool used can boost the validity of the instrument . Likewise, a mechanism for preparing teachers, be it coaching, simulation or peer mentoring can help minimize performance anxiety and boost confidence especially among young and non-tenured teachers.

The administrators and evaluation committee needs to devise alternate methodologies of assessing teacher performance as a buffer for the time constraints ,conflict of schedules and other time management issues. There is also a need for regular post conference as well as other feedback mechanisms so as to aid the teacher in identifying performance lags and gaps. Professorial development plan for teachers is commended to be drawn at a short term and long term time frames.

Given the elementary teachers’ special needs, age-based evaluation tools and policies can be alternately used so as not to disrupt the teaching process especially for classes with younger students Finally, for its output objective, this study proposes a concept map (figure 3) outlining the overall campus evaluation process. This flowchart factored in the major points raised by the respondents as well as the researcher’s analysis of data. The idea takes on a holistic approach as well as solutions-oriented process leading to a balanced development of teaching standards which includes teacher’s career growth as well as that of students learning. The map outlines the three phases (pre- visit, observation time , post visit) involved in the whole evaluation process. In each of these phases , the ideal necessary elements were outlined as needed to be executed by both parties (teachers and administrators) . Note that a policy review has been highlighted as a crucial element of the whole process.

Figure 3: Proposed Teachers Evaluation Process Flowchart for Darasamutr School

Source: Reyes, J. 2021

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